

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF MUSICAL CULTURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20302958>

Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations for increasing the effectiveness of teaching musical culture, modern pedagogical approaches, and the significance of innovative educational technologies. It also highlights the competence-based approach in music education, the use of interactive methods, information and communication technologies, and the development of students' aesthetic taste and creative thinking. The study substantiates the pedagogical factors of teacher mastery in teaching musical culture, the effective use of national musical heritage, and the formation of students' musical competence.

Keywords: musical culture, musical education, pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, musical competence, aesthetic education, creative thinking, national musical heritage, educational effectiveness.

Introduction.

One of the most important tasks facing the education system in today's process of globalization and informatization is to educate the younger generation not only as knowledgeable but also as spiritually mature individuals with aesthetic taste, who understand national values and are capable of creative thinking. In this process, the role of the science of musical culture is of particular importance. Because music is a powerful educational tool that directly affects the human heart, shaping its emotional world, worldview, aesthetic views, and spiritual image.

The subject of music culture develops students' skills in listening to, perceiving, analyzing, and performing music, as well as in deriving aesthetic pleasure from works of art. Through this subject, students become acquainted with examples of oral folk art, maqom art, national melodies and songs, and world musical culture. As a result, they develop a sense of national identity, respect for cultural heritage, artistic and aesthetic thinking, and creative activity. Therefore, the effective teaching of musical culture is one of the important components of the general education system. In the context of education, teaching the subject of musical culture based on traditional methods is insufficient. Because today's student is actively interacting with information technologies, multimedia tools, internet resources, and digital educational platforms. In such conditions, music lessons must be rich in content, methodologically diverse, interactive, and creative in nature. In particular, the combination of activities such as music listening, vocal and choral activities, rhythmic movements, creative tasks, stage performances, musical literacy, and familiarization with national instruments serves as an important factor in increasing lesson effectiveness.

Improving the effectiveness of teaching the subject of musical culture is primarily linked to a deep understanding of its theoretical foundations. Theoretical foundations are understood as the scientific and pedagogical substantiation of the goals, content, principles, methods, forms,

and means of music education. In this process, personality-oriented, competency-based, activity-based, integrative, and creative approaches are of great methodological importance. This is because music lessons should not be limited to singing or providing theoretical knowledge, but should enrich the student's emotional and aesthetic experience, develop their independent thinking, and foster creative abilities. In music education, a teacher's professional mastery is one of the decisive factors. A music teacher acts not only as a teacher who provides knowledge but also as one who instills a love for art, influences the student's inner world, and creates a creative environment. The methods he applies during the lesson, speech culture, performance skills, the ability to interpret musical works, and his ability to establish emotional communication with students determine the effectiveness of education.

Musiqa madaniyati fanini o'qitishda milliy musiqa merosidan foydalanish ham muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega. O'zbek xalq qo'shiqlari, laparlar, yallalar, maqom namunalari, baxshichilik va dostonchilik an'analari o'quvchilarda milliy g'urur, vatanparvarlik, estetik did va ma'naviy poklikni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni uyg'unlashtirish orqali o'quvchilarda keng musiqiy dunyoqarash, madaniyatlararo muloqotga tayyorlik va san'atga ongli munosabat rivojlanadi. Musiqa madaniyati fanini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish masalasi bugungi ta'lim jarayonida dolzarb ilmiy-pedagogik muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu muammoning nazariy asoslarini o'rganish musiqa ta'limining mazmunini takomillashtirish, zamonaviy metod va texnologiyalarni qo'llash, o'quvchilarning musiqiy-estetik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish hamda ta'lim sifatini oshirish imkonini beradi. Shu jihatdan mazkur maqolada musiqa madaniyati fanini samarali o'qitishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari, pedagogik shart-sharoitlari va metodik imkoniyatlarini tahlil qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Discussion

The issue of increasing the effectiveness of teaching musical culture is primarily related to the full realization of the educational, aesthetic, spiritual, and creative potential of music in the educational process. A music lesson is not a simple process of providing theoretical knowledge, but a complex pedagogical process that directly affects the inner experiences, artistic imagination, aesthetic taste, and spiritual world of the student. Therefore, it is insufficient to evaluate the effectiveness of the subject of musical culture solely by the student's ability to sing or memorize musical concepts. On the contrary, the level of the student's ability to understand, feel, analyze, express a creative attitude towards music and connect it with their life experience should be considered as the main criterion.

The theoretical foundations of music education show that during the lesson process, along with knowledge, skills, and abilities, the formation of the student's emotional and aesthetic experience plays an important role. Because music affects the human mind not only logically, but also through emotional perception. For example, when a student listens to a folk song, they feel its melody, rhythm, content, mood, and national spirit. In this process, not only musical knowledge but also cultural memory, respect for national values, and artistic sensitivity are formed. Consequently, the effectiveness of the subject "Music Culture" depends on ensuring the harmonious intellectual and emotional development of the student's personality.

In today's educational process, a competency-based approach is of particular importance in the effective teaching of the subject of musical culture. The competency-based approach implies the student's ability to apply acquired knowledge in practical activities, understand,

analyze, perform, and express an independent attitude toward a musical work. This approach focuses music lessons not only on providing theoretical information but also on forming the student as an active participant. As a result, the student is involved in the lesson process as a listener, performer, observer, and creator.

A student-centered approach also occupies an important place in teaching the subject of musical culture. Each student's musical abilities, auditory memory, sense of rhythm, vocal capabilities, and creative activity are different. Therefore, setting the same requirements for all students or evaluating them based on the same criteria can reduce the effectiveness of music education. Taking into account the individual capabilities of students during the lesson, assigning them appropriate tasks, encouraging them, and creating creative freedom creates a favorable pedagogical environment for musical development.

The use of interactive methods increases the effectiveness of music culture lessons. Methods such as "Brainstorming," "Cluster," "B-B-B," "Insert," "Discussion," "Creative Project," "Musical Quiz," and "Listen and Analyze" increase student engagement. In particular, asking questions and tasks before listening to a musical piece, focusing on important aspects during the listening process, and organizing an analytical conversation after listening develop students' musical perception. Such an approach transforms the student from a passive listener into an active analyst.

The use of information and communication technologies in the field of musical culture is also one of the important factors in increasing efficiency. Multimedia presentations, audio and video materials, electronic textbooks, virtual instrumental samples, and online music platforms will increase students' interest in the lesson. For example, rather than providing only oral information about the art of maqom or world classical music, demonstrating its performance samples in audio or video form creates a deeper understanding for students. Also, with the help of digital technologies, students can listen to the sound of various instruments, compare musical genres, and perform independent creative tasks.

The use of national musical heritage is of particular theoretical and educational importance in increasing the effectiveness of the subject of musical culture. The introduction of examples of musical heritage into the educational process, such as Uzbek folk songs, maqoms, katta ashula, bakhshi, dastan, lapar, and yalla, fosters national identity, patriotism, respect for cultural values, and aesthetic taste in students. In the process of studying examples of national music, students become acquainted with the history, traditions, lifestyle, and spiritual world of the people. This strengthens not only the artistic but also the spiritual and educational function of music education.

At the same time, it is necessary to harmoniously study examples of national and world musical culture in music culture lessons. Limiting oneself solely to national music can narrow the musical worldview of students. Familiarization with world classical music, modern musical trends, and the musical traditions of various peoples develops students' skills in intercultural communication, comparison, analysis, and aesthetic evaluation. Such an integrative approach enriches the content of the subject "Musical Culture" and shapes broad artistic thinking in students.

In teaching the subject of musical culture, a teacher's professional mastery is considered one of the most fundamental factors. In the lesson, the music teacher acts not only as a theorist but also as a performer, organizer, educator, and creator of a creative environment. His vocal

abilities, instrumental performance skills, ability to analyze musical works, emotional conduct of the lesson, and ability to awaken students' interest in art have a direct impact on educational effectiveness. In particular, a live performance by a teacher has a strong emotional impact on students and increases the educational value of the lesson.

The evaluation process also requires a unique approach in the field of musical culture. Traditional assessment is often limited to a student singing the song correctly or answering theoretical questions. However, in music education, it is necessary to evaluate the student's creative activity, sense of music, listening culture, teamwork, aesthetic expression, and the ability to perform independent creative tasks. Therefore, it is advisable to use criteria assessment, portfolios, creative works, musical projects, and self-assessment methods.

Extracurricular activities also play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of teaching the subject of musical culture. Choral clubs, ensembles, musical evenings, creative competitions, theatrical performances, and events dedicated to national holidays will further develop the students' musical abilities. Knowledge and skills acquired during the lesson are reinforced during extracurricular activities. This stabilizes the student's interest in music and increases their social activity. Effective teaching of musical culture is a multi-factor pedagogical process that requires the combination of theoretical knowledge, methodological approaches, teacher skills, technological tools, national musical heritage, and the individual characteristics of the student. To increase the effectiveness of this subject, the lesson content must be updated based on modern requirements, a creative environment oriented toward the student's personality must be created, and interactive methods and digital technologies must be purposefully applied.

Improving the effectiveness of teaching musical culture is one of the important pedagogical tasks of today's education system. This is because music education plays an important role in shaping not only students' musical knowledge and skills but also their spiritual and moral views, aesthetic taste, creative thinking, and attitude toward national values. Therefore, organizing the subject of musical culture based on modern pedagogical requirements serves as one of the main factors in improving the quality and effectiveness of education. The theoretical foundations of effective teaching of musical culture rely on competency-based, personality-oriented, activity-based, and integrative approaches. Through these approaches, students develop important competencies such as musical perception, listening culture, creative activity, aesthetic assessment, and a conscious attitude toward art. In particular, the use of interactive methods, involving students in creative activities, and enriching lessons with practical exercises significantly increase the effectiveness of music education.

Furthermore, the integration of information and communication technologies into music education creates opportunities for organizing lessons that are rich in content, interesting, and innovative. The use of multimedia tools, audio and video materials, digital platforms, and virtual educational resources strengthens students' interest in music and develops their independent learning activities. This expands the methodological possibilities of the subject of musical culture in accordance with the requirements of the modern educational environment.

Conclusion

The pedagogical significance of the effective use of national musical heritage is also substantiated. The inclusion of Uzbek folk songs, maqom art, bakhshi, and other examples of

national music in the educational process fosters a sense of national pride, patriotism, aesthetic taste, and respect for spiritual values in students. At the same time, studying examples of world musical culture expands students' artistic thinking and develops their intercultural communication competencies. It was established that the effectiveness of teaching music culture largely depends on the professional skills, methodological training, and creative approach of the teacher. The teacher must be able to apply innovative methods during the lesson, create an emotional and creative environment, and establish effective pedagogical communication with students. Because it is the teacher's pedagogical activity that is the main factor in forming students' love for art and musical interest.

In conclusion, it can be said that to increase the effectiveness of teaching musical culture, it is important to organize the educational process based on modern pedagogical technologies, widely use interactive methods, harmoniously teach national and world musical heritage, and take into account the individual and creative characteristics of students. These approaches serve to improve the quality of music education, educate a harmoniously developed generation, and enrich the aesthetic and spiritual world of young people.

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